

ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS AFFECTING NATURE

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One of the sources of environmental disasters are man-made accidents and catastrophes, since they usually cause the most significant emissions and spills of pollutants. The zones of the highest risk of environmental pollution due to man-made accidents and disasters are industrial areas, as well as large cities and metropolitan areas[1].

The largest accidents and catastrophes that have occurred in recent decades, along with the death of people, huge material damage, as a rule, caused irreparable damage to the natural environment, ecological systems of a number of regions and territories. The environmental consequences of technogenic accidents can manifest themselves for years, tens and even hundreds of years. They can be varied and multifaceted. Accidents at radiation hazardous facilities are especially dangerous. The appearance in the biosphere of new components caused by human economic activity is characterized by the term "anthropogenic pollution", which is understood as by-products generated as a result of human (society) economic activity, which, when released into the environment, change or destroy its biotic and abiotic properties.

The environment is polluted with a huge amount of industrial wastes that are toxic, as well as the ability to accumulate in the human body or food chains. Sources of air pollution are natural and anthropogenic sources. Analyzing the technosphere, we will consider only anthropogenic sources of atmospheric pollution.

Atmospheric air pollution means an increase in the concentrations of physical, chemical, biological components above the level that brings natural systems out of balance. The atmosphere is huge, and it was assumed that dust, all fumes and gases emitted by industry, power plants, transport, quickly dissipate, as if dissolving in the air. At the same time, their concentration in cities and air circulation from top to bottom were not taken into account.

Motor transport is one of the most unsafe sources of pollution for human health, since exhaust gases enter the atmosphere, where their dispersion is difficult. The composition of the exhaust gases of cars contains a large amount of nitrogen oxide, unburned carbons, aldehydes and soot, as well as carbon monoxide. It is known that thousands of people die every year due to exhaust gases, and the damage they cause to the environment is estimated at billions of dollars. Exhaust emissions affect the development of many diseases [3].

Industrial emissions also have a negative impact on human health, destroy materials and equipment, reduce the productivity of forestry and agriculture. In our time, scientists are actively working on the creation of technologies for the disposal of emissions, environmentally friendly production, and fuel. Emissions disposal technologies have been created. To clean emissions, it is necessary to build purification plants. If all chemical enterprises collected production emissions, they would receive tens of thousands of tons of such valuable substances as nitric and sulfuric acid, sulfur dioxide, fluorine, etc.

Unfortunately, the created effective production technologies are not used in most enterprises because of their high cost, and sometimes, because of the neglect of the environmental problem. In large cities, to reduce the harmful effects of air pollution on humans, special urban planning measures are used: zonal development of residential areas, when low buildings are located close to the road, then tall buildings and under their protection - children's and medical institutions; road junctions without intersections; landscaping.

The growth of anthropogenic negative impact on the environment is not always limited to the growth of only direct hazards, for example, an increase in the concentration of toxic impurities in the atmosphere. Under certain conditions, there may be secondary negative impacts that occur at the regional or global levels and have a negative impact on regions of the biosphere and significant groups of people. These include the formation of acid rain, smog, the "greenhouse effect", the destruction of the Earth's ozone layer, the accumulation of toxic and carcinogenic substances in the body of animals and fish, in food products, etc.

The emergence of technosphere dangers is based on human activity aimed at the formation and transformation of the flows of matter, energy and information in the living space. By examining and modifying these streams, you can limit their size to acceptable values. If this is not possible, then life becomes dangerous. A wasteful lifestyle is a heavy burden on the environment. One of the main reasons for the constant degradation of the natural environment around the world is the pattern of consumption and production [2].

Changes introduced by human activity into the biosphere can lead to significant changes in the Earth's climate. At the same time, it becomes necessary to foresee the possible consequences of human impact on the biosphere, since it is important to know them when planning all human activity. Many security systems are interconnected both in terms of negative impacts and means of achieving security. Ensuring the safety of human life in the technosphere is almost always inextricably linked with the solution of problems for the protection of the natural environment (reduction of emissions and discharges, etc.). This is well illustrated by the results of work to reduce toxic emissions into the atmosphere of industrial zones and, as a result, to reduce the negative impact of these zones on the environment.

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